
WHAT IS THE MAIN DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE SUKHUF OF BACTRIA AND RASMI KHAT OF THE UTHMAN MUSKHAFS?

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Abstract

The Qur'an was completely written down during the lifetime of Muhammad, peace be upon him. However, these records were kept scattered. After his death, during the caliphate of Abu Bakr Siddiq, the first collection of scattered writings was created within a year and a half. It was prepared by the leader of the scribes of revelation, Zayd bin Thabit, may Allah be pleased with him. However, this Mushaf was kept as a source in the government office until the Caliphate of Hazrat Uthman, and people did not use it. Uthman ibn Affan, may God bless him and grant him peace, saw that there was a disagreement about the words of the Qur'an and their recitation, and in order to gather the entire Muslim community in one book, he copied 6 books from the pages of Abu Bakr and sent them to the central cities, and from each book, an expert qari was taught. In this way, the discord between the Muslims was eliminated, and the looming danger was avoided.

The text of the Holy Qur'an was recorded in the same form without any changes in both stages. The fact that some researchers call the copying of the next two steps "editing" is contrary to scientific facts. Researches show that the Qur'an was preserved in the same way in the later compilations as it was first written down in the time of Muhammad (peace be upon him). There were only a few cases of disputes about the writing of certain words, and even then the Companions limited themselves to choosing one of the narrations based on ijtehad, and no one wrote it down on their own.

Keywords

Qur'an, Mushaf, pages of Abu Bakr, Mushaf of Uthman, rasmi khat.

The Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, was not satisfied with memorizing the Qur'an, but every time a revelation was revealed, he called his companions who knew how to write, and wrote down the newly revealed verses in the Arabic alphabet on various materials such as skin, bone,

stone, telling them in which surah and after which verse.¹ Public scholars studied the evidence in this regard and emphasized that this writing was not simple but was written under the control of revelation. After the Mirzas finished writing the verses, the Messenger of Allah, may God bless him and grant him peace, would read them what he had written, check them once more, and if there were any mistakes, he would correct them.²

This event was initiated from the time when the first verses began to be revealed. This is how the Holy Qur'an was written down in full letters during the time of the Holy Prophet.

During the caliphate of Abu Bakr Siddiq, more than seventy Qur'an scholars were martyred in the battle of Yamama, including Abu Huzaifa and Salim, his freed slaves. Concerned about this, with the advice of Hazrat Umar, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, Caliph Abu Bakr, may God bless him and grant him peace, ordered to collect the Holy Qur'an between two covers, and appointed Zayd bin Thabit, may God bless him and grant him peace, as the responsible leader. The Caliph's decision was made public, and an order was issued that anyone who has anything from the Qur'an should bring it to Zayd, may Allah be pleased with him.³

During the caliphate of Hazrat Uthman ibn Affan, may God bless him and grant him peace, in 24-25 years of Hijri, Huzaifa bin Yamani, may God bless him and grant him peace, was the leader of the people of Sham and participated in the invasion of Armenia and Azerbaijan with the people of Iraq. The people of Syria mainly read the recitations of Ubay ibn Ka'b and Miqdad ibn Aswad, the people of Kufa read the recitations of Ibn Mas'ud, the people of Basra read the recitations of Abu Musa Ash'ari, may God be pleased with them. When they heard a recitation that they did not know from each other, a disagreement began to arise between them. Huzaifa, may God bless him and grant him peace, was worried about this, and when they arrived in Madinah, he went to Caliph Uthman ibn Affan, may God bless him and grant him peace, and said: "Save the Ummah from falling into a dispute about the Qur'an, like the Jews and Christians," and informed him of the current situation.

Uthman ibn Affan, may God bless him and grant him peace, in consultation with a group of senior companions, sent someone to our mother Hafsa, copied and brought back the manuscript written during the time of Abu Bakr, may God bless him and grant him peace. In view of the qualities we have mentioned above and

¹ Narrated by Bukhari and Muslim.

² Narrated by Imam Hokim Zayd bin Thabit. Tabari also narrated.

³ Narrated by Bukhari, Tabari and Ibn Abu Dawud.

the fact that the Caliph copied the Mushaf that was brought from head to toe, Zayd bin Thabit, may Allah be pleased with him, was in charge of copying, and Abdullah bin Zubair, Saeed bin As, Abdurrahman bin Harith, may God be pleased with him, were appointed as his assistants. According to most scholars, the number of these mushafs was five in total. The Caliph sent one Mushaf from the copied copies to the big cities that were the centers of the Islamic world at that time in terms of science, culture, and politics, and to teach from the Mushaf, he appointed reciters who were reliable in reciting the Qur'an from the Companions or senior subordinates. They ordered to burn all the written pages and copies except for these copies, erase the writings, and then write the copies based on these copies.⁴ This event was welcomed by the entire Islamic community.⁵ Because Uthman, may Allah be pleased with him, did it with the union of twelve thousand companions.

The following differences are mentioned in the works of the two caliphs in compiling the Qur'an:

1. Abu Bakr Siddiq, may God bless him and grant him peace, collected the verses of the Qur'an from scattered writings in one place in the order taught by the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace. Uthman, may Allah be pleased with him, copied it.

Imam Nawawi said: "Uthman, may God bless him and grant him peace, copied the Mushafs from the pages on which the Companions had previously agreed, fearing that something would be added or added to the Qur'an."

2. The manuscript written by Abu Bakr Siddiq, may Allah be pleased with him, was kept as a main source in the presence of the Khalifa, the public did not use it, did not copy it, and did not teach based on it. Uthman, may God bless him and grant him peace, sent the Mushafs to the central cities, only ordering them to copy it, to teach based on it, and to receive education.

3. At the beginning of Islam, the Companions did not write anything other than the Qur'an by the Prophet, peace be upon him. Later, when people mastered the Qur'an well and were able to distinguish it from other things, it was also allowed to write some hadiths and prayers. Also, some companions used to write brief interpretations of certain words in their notebooks. In the era of Abu Bakr Siddiq, may Allah be pleased with him, when writing the Mushaf, the Holy Qur'an was compiled in its pure form, free of such additions, but other copies remained in the hands of people. Uthman, may Allah be pleased with him, took into account the

⁴ Narrations of Bukhari and Termizi.

⁵ Abu Amr Daniy.

expansion of the lands of Islam, the sharp increase in the number of Muslims, and the fact that many non-Arab peoples became Muslims, and in order to prevent people from thinking that these additions were from the Qur'an, he ordered the destruction of the Qur'anic writings, except for the manuscripts he copied.

Therefore, they did not like the mushaf that Hafsa received from Anha and returned it to themselves.

4. Abu Bakr Siddique, may God bless him and grant him peace, was content with only compiling the pure text of the Qur'an. Uthman, may Allah be pleased with him, aimed to gather the ummah in the mood of reciting that text. That is why he appointed one qari for each mushaf.

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